

Improving Content-Based Data Product Retrieval in Federated Environments with LLM and sampling

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Abstract. Data products have emerged as a powerful paradigm for managing data in both intra-enterprise and federated environments, providing structured data assets that include not only the data itself but also services, metadata, and access policies. However, a key challenge in federated environments is the discovery of relevant data products. Traditional discovery mechanisms are heavily dependent on metadata, which is often inconsistent, incomplete, or not standardized across organizations. This lack of metadata quality significantly limits the effectiveness of discovery, making it difficult for consumers to identify and retrieve the data they need. To address this challenge, we propose a content-based discovery framework that shifts the focus from metadata to the actual content of data products. Our approach uses sampling techniques to extract meaningful data representations and a tabular retrieval model for natural language queries. Directly interacting with data improves discovery accuracy, enabling effective data access in federated environments.

Keywords: Data Product · Federated Data Sharing · Content-based Discovery.

1 Introduction

The advent of data products is modifying the way organizations manage and share information [10]. Introduced within the data mesh framework [5], in this concept, data related to a specific domain is managed by a specialized team that deals, like a product, with its entire lifecycle, from collection to preparation for consumption [7]. The Data Space Support Center [3] has adopted the concept of data products as data sharing units that contain not only data and services but also metadata that describe resources and associated licensing agreements. These metadata are usually used to drive the *discovery* of data product, but they are often inconsistent and incomplete [6], and the data discovery is also worsened by diverse governance and a lack of standards.

To improve the efficacy of discovery, our work proposes an innovative framework based on a *content-based discovery* approach that directly exploits the data content rather than relying on metadata. Specifically, the proposed method assumes that the data involved is structured data, so the framework extracts a

significant sample from the data of each data product and leverages a tabular retriever model to perform content-based queries across all the data products of the federation, thus overcoming the limitations imposed by different governance policies and lack of metadata quality.

The paper is organized as follows. After the discussion on relevant work in the literature presented in Sec. 2, Sec. 3 presents the proposed LLM-based data product discovery process architecture, and Sec. 4 analyses the data product sampling problem. An evaluation of the proposed approach is discussed in Sec. 5 and Sec. 6 concludes the paper outlining possible future directions.

2 Related Works

In federated data architectures, data discovery [11] is often hindered by meta-data that is inconsistent, incomplete, or lacks a common standard [6]. This is confirmed by a recent study [12] stating the few dataset are described leveraging metadata standards.

Although still at an early stage [1], content-based discovery techniques promise to improve the accuracy of results by exploiting the content of data, for instance, by leveraging embedding and vector-based retrieval. Due to the growth in the size of datasets, generating embeddings for the entire content is often unfeasibly expensive. The challenge of small context windows in Large Language Models has been extensively studied in the literature through various approaches [2]. However, an interesting alternative to overcome this limitation is the use of sampling and clustering techniques to extract significant data samples that are then fed into the LLMs to bypass the context window constraint.

Various sampling approaches, including random, systematic, and stratified sampling [13], provide computationally efficient solutions but do not always effectively capture the information characteristics of the data. To improve the significance of the samples, clustering-based methods can be used: e.g., mixed-attributes such as k-means [8] or k-medoids [9], the latter more robust to outliers than k-means. In addition, clustering methods such as DBSCAN and the improved version K-DBSCAN have been widely used to detect clusters of arbitrary shape in the data, starting from regions of data with high density.

3 General Architecture

The proposed LLM-based data product discovery process (see Fig. 1) is conceived as a federation service that is offered, for instance, to all members of a given data space. Considering the definition proposed by the DSSC [4], a federation service is a service that enables secure and regulated data sharing by managing various aspects, including but not limited to policy compliance, access control, and discoverability, while ensuring compliance with relevant regulations.

In this context, the end user of the framework is a data consumer who wants to discover specific data within the federation of which they are a participant.

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed Framework

The objective of the framework is to facilitate the discovery of only those data that are relevant to their query and to which they actually have a right of access¹.

The content-based discovery process starts with the data producer, who has created a properly structured data product according to the organization’s and federation’s data governance policies. A valid data product must include the data, the APIs for accessing the data, and a set of access policies that define how and by whom the data can be used.

With the APIs, the framework extracts data from the data product. Through augmentation and sampling, a representative subset of the original data, called sample data, is generated. This *sample data* is essential for enabling efficient discovery, as it captures the key characteristics of the data product while being much smaller in size.

When working in a federated setting, some organizations may prefer, or may be required, not to store their data outside a given region unless it has been anonymized. For instance, an organization collecting sensitive data regulated by the European GDPR may only store that data outside the European Union if it has first been anonymized. These restrictions are usually expressed in the policies attached to the data products. To address these constraints, our content-based data product discovery framework includes an optional de-identification step when policies or the vector database’s location require anonymizing generated sample data before storage.

After this optional de-identification process, an *embedding* is generated from the sample data using a table retrieval model, which will be stored in a vector database containing the embeddings of all data products in the federation.

The content-based discovery process continues when the data consumer, interacts with it. Each data consumer is part of an organization and has a specific role within said organization that determines its data access permissions. Data consumers aim to find relevant information within the federation by submitting natural language queries. This allows them to search for data products that meet

¹ It is worth highlighting that in this paper, the issues related to the access authorization are not covered. It will be the objective of future work.

their needs while adhering to organizational policies and access restrictions. By leveraging the same tabular retriever model used to generate the sample data embeddings, an embedding of the query is generated, and the vector database is queried.

The vector database returns a list of sample data satisfying the query, together with a relevance score. A relevance metric and a distance metric are calculated to select only the best performing samples data. The data products whose sample data have been selected are then forwarded, together with the role of the data consumer, to the policy compliance node. The policy compliance node is a complex component of the frameworks that is responsible for ensuring compliance with the policies. In fact, the policy compliance node encapsulates a policy compliance engine, which is able to read the policies of a data product and the identity of the data consumer, i.e., their role and organization. Given these information, the objective of this component is to generate a tailored version of the gathered data products that contains only the subset of data that the data consumer has the right to access based on their identity. The generated data products are then finally given to the data consumers.

By leveraging these components, the proposed framework greatly simplifies the process of data discovery and access in a federated data product architecture. At the same time, the framework ensures that access to data is highly granular by strictly complying with the access policies defined by the data producers.

4 Data Product Sampling

Within the framework presented in Sec. 3, this paper focuses on the process of sample data generation and data retrieval. The goal is to extract a meaningful sample of the content of the data product and use it for content-based discovery, overcoming the limitations of metadata, and to discover relevant data via a natural language query. The need for sample data arises from the limitations imposed by the context window of artificial intelligence models, i.e., the maximum input size that a model can process.

4.1 Generating a Sample Data

The process of generating sample data involves the use of a sampling algorithm, an LLM generative model, and a tabular retrieval model to support content-based discovery based on sample data effectively. The red rectangle in Fig. 1 encloses the main steps. Having obtained the data from the data product exploiting the offered API, two different sampling methods have been considered.

The first is the *Random* sampling that, as the name suggests, randomly chooses a subset of records in the data product, and it is leveraged as a baseline in the discovery process. A second method is based on *DBSCAN with an augmentation phase* that utilizes the DBSCAN algorithm to generate a sample data and leverages a generative LLM model, specifically GPT-4o mini, to augment the column descriptions. The DBSCAN clustering algorithm identifies patterns

in the data based on density and is used to divide the data into distinct homogeneous groups. Since data products can contain both categorical and numerical data, the distance matrix for the DBSCAN clustering algorithm is calculated utilizing the Gower distance [14], which is often used for the similarity analysis of mixed data. Gower distance is defined as a measure that calculates the similarity between two elements. It normalizes each variable to compare them equally and then averages the differences between the values. The purpose of the augmentation step is to improve the quality of the descriptive columns of the sample data, making them more representative of the original content and thus optimizing the effectiveness of the content-based discovery. The generative LLM model produces a new list of descriptors which, after being cleansed, replaces the original one, creating an *augmented sample data*.

From the generated clusters, a *sample data* of 150 elements is selected with a distribution proportional to the density of the clusters, ensuring that the sample data remains representative of the original data product. The size of the sample data is constrained by the limited context window of the tabular retriever model. At the same time, from the data extracted from the data product, leveraging a random sampling algorithm, we generate *random sample data*. If the data product contains fewer than 150 elements, sampling is not required, and all data are included in both the sample data and the random sample data.

As per Fig. 1, a sample day may undergo a de-identification process if it is required due to the content of the data. Next, both sample data are converted into the appropriate format and passed to a table retriever model, such as mpnet-base-v2-table², which generates the embeddings of the sample data. These embeddings are finally stored in a vector database, making the framework ready for content-based searching.

4.2 Discovering a Data Product

The process of discovering sample data begins with the query of a data consumer and follows the workflow illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Process of discovering data products

Initially, the query is processed by the same tabular retriever model that embedded the sample data. The vector database is then queried, and the data consumer can choose how many data products to retrieve; for instance, let's

² <https://huggingface.co/deepset/all-mpnet-base-v2-table>

consider only the top 20 results. These results are transformed into a list that contains the location of each data product along with a score that reflects the relevance of the sample data, and, by extension, the data product, to the query.

It is expected that both types of sample data will be retrieved from a given query due to the presence of both the augmented sample data and the random sample data in the vector database. The random sample data consists entirely of randomly selected samples from the data product, whereas the augmented sample data provides a density-based representation with augmented data columns that more accurately reflect the content of the product. Therefore, the two sample types produce different results. By comparing these scores, it is possible to calculate the following two metrics.

Relevance metric. $Rel(Q, DP) \in [0..1]$. Calculate how pertinent a data product DP is to the query Q , where 0 means not and 1 very relevant to the query. For each retrieved sample data, the relevance metric is calculated as the mean of the scores. If only a single sample from a data product is retrieved, the relevance metric corresponds to that sample’s score.

$$Rel = (Score_{Random} + Score_{Augmented})/2 \quad (1)$$

Distance metric. $Dis(Q, DS) \in [0..1]$. It measures the precision of the query in relation to the data product’s content. Thus, a sample data containing mostly only the data requested in the query will have a distance close to 1. The distance metric is evaluated using the following sigmoid function:

$$Dis = (1 + e^{-(\alpha x + \beta)})^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where α and β are parameters that place the curve within a range of 0 to 0.5, representing the minimum and maximum possible values for the input, corresponding to 20 and -2, respectively.

A higher relevance metric indicates a more relevant data product; at the same time, a higher distance metric signifies a more precise query. In fact, where the query closely matches the data product, the augmented data sample tends to perform better than the random data sample. On the other hand, if the query is contextually relevant but not precisely matched to the stored data, both metrics will typically receive a similar score and thus produce a lower distance metric.

5 Evaluation

The validation of the approach is based on datasets from Kaggle that could be seen as representative of our data products. Specifically, they are grouped in four categories: sales (four datasets), environment (three datasets), lifestyle (four datasets), and entertainment (four datasets). These datasets were chosen to ensure a heterogeneous set of data while maintaining some degree of similarity to evaluate the effectiveness of the approach.

We simulated a data consumer accessing the data by submitting queries to the vector database. Specifically, these queries were designed to evaluate whether

Sample Name	Sample Type	Score
Car_Price	Random Sample Data	59
Car_Price	Augmented Sample Data	50
E_Commerce	Augmented Sample Data	36
Synthetic_Sales	Augmented Sample Data	33
Synthetic_Sales	Random Sample Data	30
Daily_Nutrition	Augmented Sample Data	27

Table 1. Discovery Results for Query Q1

Sample Name	Sample Type	Score	Rel	Dis
CO2_Emissions	Random Data Sample	0.48	0.46	0.27
	Augmented Data Sample	0.44		
Rainfall	Augmented Data Sample	0.30	0.30	-
Nutrition	Augmented Data Sample	0.29	0.29	-
E-commerce	Random Data Sample	0.28	0.28	-
Car_Price	Random Data Sample	0.26	0.26	-

Table 2. Discovery Results for Query Q2

the framework could identify the most relevant data products based on their content and the quality of the previously defined metrics. In order to evaluate the framework of the gathered data, we propose two test query, as presented in the next paragraphs. Each query has been studied to reflect the content of their context while targeting mainly one specific dataset.³

Q1: Dataset containing details about car models sold. The objective of query *Q1* is to discover data on sold cars. However, since the vector database contains multiple sample data related to sales, this scenario provides an interesting test of our framework’s performance. Table 1 presents the top six scores of the query with the *Rel* and *Dis* values, for the results within 20% of the higher relevance score. In this case, only the *Car_Price* dataset satisfies this constraint, and the distance metric is 0.46.

This outcome demonstrates that the framework effectively identifies the most relevant dataset in the database and that the query is quite accurate with respect to the content of the dataset. In fact, the *Car_Price* dataset contains data about car models, sold price, and additional attributes such as car brands and manufacturing years.

Q2: Dataset containing CO₂ emissions. Query *Q2* has been intentionally formulated vaguely, specifying only an interest in CO₂ emissions. The scores resulting from this query are listed in Table 2. Applying the same 20% relevance threshold, the output of query *Q2* is *CO2_Emissions* with a distance metric of 0.27. While this result indicates a relevant match, the query could be refined to better capture the dataset’s content. By slightly augmenting the query to *Q2.2: Dataset containing data about CO2 emissions by continent*, the retrieved dataset remains the same with an unchanged relevance metric but with a significant improvement in the distance metric, going from 0.27 to 0.94. This improvement suggests that the refined query better aligns with the dataset’s content, demonstrating the impact of query specificity on retrieval accuracy.

³ For a complete description of the selected datasets and additional queries considered in the validation, refer to <https://github.com/TheFalco/Complete-Evaluation>

6 Conclusion and Future Work

The solution proposed in this paper enables the generation of representative samples of data products and the use of a tabular retrieval model to support the content-based user's queries, thus facilitating the discovery of relevant data in federated environments. Our framework has two metrics to evaluate discovered data. They identify relevant data products and indicate the query's relevance to their content. This metric allows data consumers to improve their queries by adding or removing details to discover more relevant data products.

In future work, we aim to further explore the definition and implementation of the policy compliance node, with a focus on automatic access control management. This aspect is critical to ensure that access to data products is regulated in a secure manner that complies with the policies defined by the data providers. The integration of access control mechanisms will further refine the granularity of permissions and improve the overall security of the framework.

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